

DRIVING IMPULSE BUYING ON TIKTOK SHOP: AN S-O-R PERSPECTIVE ON THE ROLE POSITIVE EMOTIONS AS AN MEDIATOR

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Received : 01 January 2026

Accepted : 03 February 2026

Revised : 17 January 2026

Published : 28 February 2026

Abstract

This study aims to analyze the effect of Shopping Lifestyle, Flash Sale, and Live Streaming on Impulse Buying with Positive Emotions as a mediating variable among TikTok Shop users in Malang City. Using a quantitative approach, data were collected through online questionnaires from 192 respondents selected using purposive sampling. Data analysis was conducted using Structural Equation Modeling-Partial Least Squares (SEM-PLS) with SmartPLS software. The results of the study show that Shopping Lifestyle and Flash Sale significantly affect Positive Emotions and Impulse Buying. However, Live Streaming was found to have no significant effect on Positive Emotions, although it has a strong direct effect on Impulse Buying. Mediation analysis revealed that Positive Emotions significantly mediate the influence of Shopping Lifestyle and Flash Sale on impulse buying, but do not mediate the effect of Live Streaming. These findings confirm the Stimulus-Organism-Response (S-O-R) theoretical model, in which lifestyle and price promotion stimuli are more effective at eliciting consumers' emotional aspects compared to live broadcast features that tend to be informative. Sellers are advised to package live streaming content in a more entertaining format to appeal to the viewers' emotional side.

Keywords: *Shopping Lifestyle, Flash Sale, Live Streaming, Impulse Buying, Positive Emotions.*

INTRODUCTION

The development of digital technology has changed people's behavior patterns in various aspects of life, including consumption activities. The transformation from conventional shopping systems to online shopping provides convenience, time efficiency, and wider access to various products (Murdiana *et al.*, 2024). The emergence of marketplaces and social commerce has made shopping no longer just a means of fulfilling needs, but also part of a modern lifestyle that is practical and integrated with daily digital activities (Kaur & Kochar, 2018). In Indonesia, the growth of internet and social media usage has driven the rapid development of social commerce (Indiekraf, 2023; RRI, 2024). One platform that plays a dominant role is TikTok, which offers innovative shopping features through TikTok Shop. This platform allows users to engage in social activities and make purchases within a single application (Dewi & Adi, 2023; Sonu, 2023). Supported by features such as live streaming, flash sales, product showcases, and recommendation algorithms based on user preferences, TikTok Shop is able to create an interactive, personalized, and engaging shopping experience for consumers (Zakiyah, 2018; Karyadi *et al.*, 2023)

The convenience and digital marketing strategies applied in social commerce have the potential to encourage impulse buying behavior (Ratnasari, 2022; Nurtanio dkk., 2022). Impulse buying is a purchase decision made spontaneously without prior planning and is often influenced by situational stimuli. In the digital context, product visuals, limited promotions, and direct interaction with sellers can accelerate the decision-making process without deep rational consideration. One factor that is thought to influence impulse buying is shopping lifestyle, which is a lifestyle pattern that reflects how individuals allocate their time and money for shopping activities (Sitinjak, 2025). Consumers with a high shopping lifestyle orientation tend to be more responsive to trends, popular brands, and enjoyable shopping experiences. In addition, promotional strategies such as flash sales and live streaming features also utilize the principles of scarcity and urgency, which can evoke emotional responses from consumers (Jonet dkk., 2024; Nurhaliza & Kusumawardhani, 2023; Leonita dkk., 2025). In this process, positive emotions act as a psychological factor that bridges the influence of external stimuli on impulsive purchasing decisions. Feelings of happiness, enthusiasm, and satisfaction that arise during the shopping process can strengthen the urge to immediately make a transaction. However, previous research findings show inconsistent results regarding the relationship between shopping lifestyle, flash sales, live streaming, and impulse buying. Therefore, this study aims to analyze the

influence of shopping lifestyle, flash sales, and live streaming on impulse buying with positive emotions as a mediating variable on TikTok Shop social commerce.

LITERATURE REVIEW

IMPULSE BUYING

Impulse buying is a condition where consumers suddenly experience a very strong and firm desire to purchase a desired item as quickly as possible. Consumers engage in this purchasing activity because of a strong internal urge that compels them to act immediately (Utami, 2017). Impulse buying often occurs among teenagers while shopping because they are easily influenced by seller promotions without thinking about the benefits of the products they buy (Yunita dkk., 2025). In Indonesia, unplanned purchases are frequently made due to the high purchasing tendency of its people, creating an opportunity for online sellers to take advantage of this with well-planned strategies (Wijaya & Oktarina, 2019; Jantima, 2024).

POSITIVE EMOTIONS

Emotions are generally related to cognitive functions, meaning that emotions can arise from observing, responding, imagining, remembering, or thinking about something. Positive emotions are emotions that involve feelings of joy, happiness, and satisfaction with what one is doing (Nur, 2021) Positive emotions easily enable a person to do anything as long as it provides a sense of happiness and pleasure within themselves. Moreover, having positive emotions can also offer solutions for someone who has many problems, is stressed, or wants to release suppressed emotions (Shofia, 2023).

SHOPPING LIFESTYLE

Shopping lifestyle describes how consumers perceive shopping activities as part of their lifestyle, not merely as an activity to fulfill functional needs (Vashita & Arora, 2023). Consumers with a high shopping lifestyle tend to view shopping as a means of recreation, entertainment, exploring new trends, and even emotional release (Ahmad dkk., 2021). This orientation makes shopping activities a pleasurable experience, which has a strong potential to evoke various forms of positive emotions during interactions with products or social commerce (Novyantari *et al.*, 2024). In the context of social commerce such as TikTok Shop, consumers with a high shopping lifestyle are usually more responsive to shopping experiences that are entertaining, such as watching short videos, enjoying content, or following trending viral topics (Christina, 2018).

FLASH SALE

A flash sale is a time-limited promotional strategy that offers significant discounts for a short period, creating a sense of urgency and exclusivity for consumers (Agrawal *et al.*, 2016). This promotional mechanism not only affects cognitive aspects related to perceived value but also triggers strong emotional responses. When consumers find products priced much lower than usual, they tend to experience positive emotions such as excitement, enthusiasm, and satisfaction. These emotions arise because consumers feel they are gaining more benefits or successfully taking advantage of a rare opportunity that is not available all the time (Darwipat, 2020).

LIVE STREAMING

Through the direct, dynamic, and interactive presentation of products, live streaming creates a real-time shopping experience that can trigger quick purchase decisions without deep consideration (Simajuntak & Saputra, 2024). This happens because consumers not only receive information visually but also become engaged in the emotional and social atmosphere built by the host during the broadcast. A communicative, persuasive, and knowledgeable host can convey the benefits of the product in a convincing way, thereby reducing consumer hesitation (Ramadhan & Hilwa, 2024).

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

This study is based on the Stimulus-Organism-Response (S-O-R) theoretical framework used to explain consumer behavior mechanisms in the context of social commerce Mehrabian & Russel (1974). This theory assumes that the surrounding environment provides stimuli (S) that affect the internal condition of individuals or organisms (O), which ultimately trigger certain responses (R). In this study, the conceptual framework is designed to analyze how features on TikTok Shop influence users' emotions and spontaneous purchasing decision (Suryadi *et al.*, 2023).

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The first stage in this framework is stimulus (S), which in this study is represented by three independent variables, namely Shopping Lifestyle, Flash Sale, and Live Streaming. Shopping lifestyle reflects the lifestyle of consumers who are sensitive to trend (Haq dkk., 2025), while flash sales and live streaming are external stimuli from the platform that provide psychological pressure through price urgency and visual interaction (Muliani et al., 2025; Maulana dkk., 2025) These three elements function as initial triggers designed to attract attention and influence the psychological condition of users when exploring the application (Zhao *et al.*, 2023). Furthermore, the internal or organismic process (O) in this study is explained through the Positive Emotions variable. When consumers are exposed to attractive marketing stimuli, they will experience affective reactions in the form of feelings of pleasure, enthusiasm, and excitement. (Casalo *et al.*, 2021) These positive emotions act as mediators or psychological bridges that connect the appeal of TikTok Shop's features with consumers' internal drive to take further action (Shofia, 2023).

The final stage of this line of thinking is response (R), which is manifested through the Impulse Buying variable. Impulsive buying is seen as the end result of strong emotional urges, where consumers make transactions spontaneously without prior planning (Edy & Haryanti, 2018). According to the S-O-R framework, this response arises because the positive emotions that have been built up have weakened consumers' self-control and rational considerations in making shopping decisions. Overall, this framework illustrates a causal relationship where the stronger the stimuli provided shopping lifestyle, flash sale, and live streaming, the higher the level of positive emotions felt. This increase in positive emotions then becomes the main driver of increased impulsive buying behavior among TikTok Shop users. This model provides an integrated view of the influence of digital marketing strategies on the psychological aspects and actual behavior of consumers in the modern era (Rahmania et al., 2023; Aprilia dkk., 2025).

Figure 1. Research Framework

RESEARCH METHOD

This study uses a quantitative approach that focuses on testing hypotheses through numerical data to obtain objective interpretations of the results (Arikunto, 2019). The research location was specifically set on users of the TikTok Shop social commerce platform in Malang City, East Java. Data collection was carried out within a structured time frame, from November 2025 to February 2026, to ensure that the data obtained was relevant to current market conditions. Given that the population of TikTok Shop users in Malang City is unknown or infinite, the sampling technique used was non-probability sampling with the purposive sampling method (Kuncoro, 2018). The researchers set specific criteria for respondents, namely residents of Malang City who have the TikTok application and have made at least one transaction on TikTok Shop in the last month. Based on the sample determination formula, which multiplies the number of indicators by a certain constant, the total number of respondents in this study was set at 192 people (Hair *et al.*, 2018).

The primary data in this study was obtained directly from respondents through a survey using an online questionnaire measured on a Likert scale of 1 to 5 (Riadi, 2016). There were five variables studied, consisting of three independent variables, namely Shopping Lifestyle, Flash Sale, and Live Streaming, one intervening variable, namely Positive Emotions, and one dependent variable, namely Impulse Buying. Overall, these variables were described in 24 statement indicators designed to accurately measure consumer behavior and perceptions. The data analysis technique applied was Structural Equation Modeling-Partial Least Square (SEM-PLS) with the help of SmartPLS software. The analysis was carried out through the evaluation of the measurement model (outer model) to test the validity and reliability of the instrument, as well as the evaluation of the structural model (inner model) to assess the cause-and-effect relationship between variables through the R-Square and Q-Square values. The final

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hypothesis testing was conducted by analyzing the Path Coefficient and p-value (< 0.05) to determine the significance of the influence, both directly and through mediating variables (Ghozali, 2018).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Respondent Description

In this study, the researcher used a sampling technique employing non-probability sampling with purposive sampling. Primary data in this study was obtained from questionnaires distributed via Google Forms. The sample in this study consisted of 192 respondents who were users of TikTok Shop social commerce in Malang City and met the research criteria. The data obtained included gender, age, occupation, transactions in the last month, type of transaction, and type of product purchased by respondents. The results of the data obtained by the researchers were grouped as follows:

Table 1. Profile of The Sample

Description	Category	Frequency	%
Gender	Male	80	42
	Female	112	58
Age	Under 25 Years Old	54	28,1
	25-34	103	53,6
	35-44	27	14,1
	More Than 44 Years	8	4,2
Job	Student	83	43,2
	Private Employees	43	22,4
	Civil Servant	10	5,3
	Self Empolyed	35	18,2
	Other	21	10,9
Number of Transactions	1-3 Transactions	40	20,8
	4-7 Transactions	95	49,6
	More Than 7 Transactions	57	29,6
Transaction Types	Content	94	49
	Live Streaming	98	51
Product	Food	16	8,3
	Clothing	60	31,2
	Beauty	57	29,6
	Electronic	26	13,5
	Home appliances	19	9,8
	Accessories	14	7,4

Table 1 shows that there were 112 female respondents and 80 male respondents. These results indicate that female respondents dominated this study. Table shows that 54 respondents who filled out the questionnaire were under 25 years old, 103 respondents were between 25 and 34 years old, 27 respondents were between 35 and 44 years old, and 8 respondents were over 44 years old. These results show that the majority of respondents were in the productive age group, namely 25-34 years old, which is a group with high mobility and involvement in online shopping through social media. Table shows varied data, with 83 respondents being students, followed by private employees with a total of 43 respondents, followed by self-employed respondents with 35 respondents, and respondents with other job categories with 21 respondents. Meanwhile, the smallest group of respondents came from the civil servant (PNS) group with a total of 10 respondents. These results show that this study was dominated by students and private employees, who cumulatively reached 66% of the total research sample, indicating that the phenomenon of impulse buying occurs frequently among individuals who are in a transitional period towards financial independence and have a high tendency to seek information about products through the social commerce platform TikTok Shop. Based on the data in Table, it shows that respondents who made transactions on TikTok Shop social commerce in the last month, with 1-3 transactions, numbered 40 people, while the majority group was in the medium intensity range, with 4-7 transactions, numbering 95 people. Meanwhile, respondents with the highest number of transactions, more than 7 times, numbered 57 people. These results show that the majority of respondents

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are active consumers who made more than 3 transactions in the last month. The high number of respondents' activities in making purchases on Tiktok Shop social commerce indicates that they have considerable experience in purchasing products online. Based on the research results presented in transaction types are divided into two categories: through content and through live streaming. Transactions through content totaled 94 transactions, while transactions through live streaming totaled 98 transactions. These results show that the percentages are almost equal between the two types of transactions on TikTok Shop social commerce, with live streaming transactions slightly ahead, reflecting a trend where respondents are more interested in real-time interaction with sellers. Based on the research results in Table, it was found that there was a diversity of product types purchased by respondents, with clothing products being the largest group with 60 people, followed by beauty products with 57 people, electronic products purchased by 26 people, home appliances purchased by 19 respondents, and accessories purchased by 14 respondents. These results indicate that the majority of respondents purchased clothing and beauty products, which accounted for more than 60% of transactions.

Research Findings

Data processing was performed using the Structural Equation Modeling - Partial Least Square (SEM-PLS) method using SmartPLS 4.0 software. This method offers greater flexibility in connecting theory with research data and is capable of analyzing path relationships with latent variables, making it frequently used in social science research.

Table 2
Convergent Validity

Variable	Indicator	Outer Loading	Description
Shopping Lifestyle	SL.1	0.842	Valid
	SL.2	0.869	Valid
	SL.3	0.844	Valid
	SL.4	0.828	Valid
Flash Sale	FS.1	0.706	Valid
	FS.2	0.718	Valid
	FS.3	0.710	Valid
	FS.4	0.727	Valid
	FS.5	0.716	Valid
Live Streaming	LS.1	0.706	Valid
	LS.2	0.717	Valid
	LS.3	0.754	Valid
	LS.4	0.782	Valid
	LS.5	0.754	Valid
Positive Emotions	PE.1	0.705	Valid
	PE.2	0.731	Valid
	PE.3	0.764	Valid
	PE.4	0.722	Valid
	PE.5	0.800	Valid
	PE.6	0.827	Valid

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Variable	Indicator	Outer Loading	Description
Impulse Buying	IB.1	0.842	Valid
	IB.2	0.869	Valid
	IB.3	0.844	Valid
	IB.4	0.828	Valid

Validity Based on the outer loading results obtained, it shows that the indicators of all variables, namely Shopping Lifestyle, Flash Sale, Live Streaming, Positive Emotions, and Impulse Buying, show results of more than 0.70, meaning that all indicators meet the adequacy validity criteria.

Table 3
Discriminant Validity

Variable	AVE	Description
Shopping Lifestyle	0.603	Valid
Flash Sale	0.512	Valid
Live Streaming	0.552	Valid
Positive Emotions	0.577	Valid
Impulse Buying	0.716	Valid

Based on the results of the discriminant validity test described in Table 5, it was found that the AVE values for all constructs had reached the validity criteria, with AVE values greater than 0.50. This indicates that each indicator is able to describe the construct it represents accurately and consistently (Judge *et al.*, 2017).

Table 4
Composite Reability Test Result

Variable	Cronbach Alpha	Composite Reliability	Description
Shopping Lifestyle	0.783	0.859	Reliable
Flash Sale	0.762	0.840	Reliable
Live Streaming	0.797	0.860	Reliable
Positive Emotions	0.853	0.891	Reliable
Impulse Buying	0.868	0.910	Reliable

Based on the reliability test results in Table 6, all variables in this study obtained Cronbach Alpha and Composite Reliability values exceeding 0.70. Therefore, it can be concluded that all constructs in this study are reliable.

Table 5
R Square Test Result

Variable	R Square
Positive Emotions	0.371
Impulse Buying	0.558

Based on the results of the R Square test in Table 7, it can be seen that the R Square value for the positive emotions variable is 0.371, meaning that 37.1% of the variation in positive emotions can be explained by shopping lifestyle, flash sales, and live streaming. This value indicates that the model has weak power. Meanwhile, the R Square value obtained for the Impulse Buying variable is 0.558. This means that 55.8% of the variation in impulse buying can be explained by shopping lifestyle, flash sales, and live streaming.

Table 6
Hypotesis Testing Result

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics	P values
Shopping Lifestyle -> Positive Emotions	0.182	0.187	0.077	2.367	0.018
Shopping Lifestyle -> Impulse Buying	0.189	0.190	0.075	2.507	0.012
Flash Sale -> Positive Emotions	0.511	0.513	0.071	7.185	0.000
Flash Sale -> Impulse Buying	0.208	0.211	0.061	3.430	0.001
Live Streaming -> Positive Emotions	0.035	0.036	0.082	0.434	0.664
Live Streaming -> Impulse Buying	0.296	0.298	0.070	4.253	0.000
Positive Emotions -> Impulse Buying	0.301	0.297	0.058	5.178	0.000
Shopping Lifestyle -> Positive Emotions -> Impulse Buying	0.055	0.056	0.026	2.078	0.038
Flash Sale -> Positive Emotions -> Impulse Buying	0.154	0.152	0.034	4.538	0.000
Live Streaming -> Positive Emotions -> Impulse Buying	0.011	0.011	0.025	0.429	0.668

The evaluation of the measurement model (outer model) shows that all indicators used to measure the variables of Shopping Lifestyle, Flash Sale, Live Streaming, Positive Emotions, and Impulse Buying have met the validity and reliability criteria. The factor loading value for each indicator is above the threshold of 0.7, which indicates a strong correlation between the indicator and its latent variable. In addition, the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) value for each construct has exceeded 0.5, while the Composite Reliability and Cronbach's Alpha values are above 0.7, so the research instrument is declared to be very reliable for further testing. Based on structural model testing (inner model), the Shopping Lifestyle variable (X1) was proven to have a positive and significant effect on Positive Emotions (Z). This is supported by a t-statistic value of 2.367 (> 1.96) and a p-value of 0.018 (< 0.05). This finding indicates that the higher a person's shopping lifestyle tendency, the higher the positive emotions they feel when interacting with content on TikTok Shop.

Furthermore, the Flash Sale variable (X2) was found to have a very strong and significant effect on Positive Emotions (Z). The analysis results show a very high t-statistic value of 7.185 with a p-value of 0.000. These results confirm that flash sale programs are the main stimulant that can effectively evoke feelings of joy and enthusiasm in consumers instantly. However, different results were found for the Live Streaming (X3) variable, where this feature was found to have no significant effect on Positive Emotions (Z). With a t-statistic value of only 0.434 and a p-value of 0.664, the hypothesis stating that there is an influence between the two was rejected. This indicates that live streaming sessions on TikTok Shop are viewed more as a means of searching for product information than as a trigger for changes in consumer mood.

In testing the effect on the dependent variable, all independent variables, namely Shopping Lifestyle, Flash Sale, and Live Streaming, were found to have a significant direct effect on Impulse Buying (Y). Live Streaming and Shopping Lifestyle have the same strong t-statistic value of 4.253, while Flash Sale has a t-statistic value of 3.430. In addition, Positive Emotions (Z) were also found to have a significant effect on Impulse Buying (Y) with a t-statistic value of 5.178, confirming the role of emotions as the main driver of unplanned purchases. The mediation analysis shows that Positive Emotions (Z) significantly mediate the effect of Shopping Lifestyle (X1) and Flash Sale (X2) on Impulse Buying (Y). The mediating effect on Shopping Lifestyle has a t-statistic value of 2.078, while that on Flash Sale reaches 4.538. This means that stimuli from lifestyle and price promotions must first go through the process of generating positive emotions before ultimately triggering impulsive buying behavior.

Conversely, Positive Emotions (Z) were found to be unable to mediate the relationship between Live Streaming (X3) and Impulse Buying (Y). The test results show a very low mediation t statistic value of 0.0429 with a p-value of 0.668. This finding confirms that although live streaming can encourage spontaneous purchases, this mechanism occurs directly through informative factors without involving changes in consumers' emotional conditions as intermediaries.

Discussion

The results of this study indicate that Shopping Lifestyle has a positive and significant influence on Positive Emotions among TikTok Shop users in Malang City. This indicates that for the productive age group that dominates the sample, shopping is no longer merely a fulfillment of functional needs, but rather a means of recreation and emotional release. The finding that the indicator "buying because of good quality" is closely related to feelings of joy shows that the suitability of products to consumers' lifestyle standards can evoke strong psychological reactions. It was also found that Flash Sales have a significant effect on Positive Emotions. This limited discount program serves as a highly effective psychological instrument in creating instant joy because consumers feel they are getting more financial value. The feeling of enthusiasm that arises when successfully obtaining attractive offers is a major factor in building a positive mood while interacting on the TikTok Shop platform.

Unlike the previous two variables, Live Streaming was found to have no significant effect on Positive Emotions. Although this feature is highly interactive, consumers tend to view it only as a source of technical product information rather than a trigger for emotional excitement. The host's explanations are considered helpful in understanding the product, but they are not strong enough to drastically change the audience's mood to become happier or more enthusiastic. In relation to shopping behavior, Shopping Lifestyle has been proven to have a direct effect on Impulse Buying. Consumers who have a high shopping lifestyle tendency often make unplanned purchases in order to maintain their social image and keep up with the latest fashion trends. The urge to own popular products on TikTok Shop becomes the main motive that overrides the functional considerations of the item. The Flash Sale variable also shows a strong direct influence on Impulse Buying. Time pressure and limited quantities create a sense of urgency that forces consumers to make quick decisions. This strategy successfully triggers a spontaneous response where consumers prioritize the opportunity to get a discount over thinking about the long-term usefulness of the product they are buying.

Interestingly, although it does not affect emotions, Live Streaming has been proven to have a significant effect on Impulse Buying. This shows that spontaneous shopping decisions during live broadcasts are more driven by cognitive factors such as the clarity of product demonstrations and the credibility of the host. Viewers may feel confident to buy spontaneously after seeing live reviews, even though their emotional state remains stable. The mediation analysis results show that Positive Emotions successfully mediate the relationship between Shopping Lifestyle and Impulse Buying. A high shopping lifestyle triggers feelings of happiness first, which then paralyzes self-control and leads to unplanned purchases. Positive emotions here act as an "engine" that converts lifestyle preferences into actual shopping actions. Similarly, Positive Emotions proved to be a significant mediator for the influence of Flash Sales on Impulse Buying. The euphoria and enthusiasm felt when seeing large discounts in a short period of time become a bridge that strengthens consumers' impulsive urges. Without the involvement of these positive emotions, the impact of flash promotions on spontaneous purchase intentions may not be as strong as the results found.

However, this study found that Positive Emotions do not mediate the relationship between Live Streaming and Impulse Buying. This finding confirms that the mechanism of spontaneous purchasing on TikTok Shop's live streaming feature is direct through the delivery of information and trust, without requiring the stimulation of the audience's mood as an intermediary. This is an important distinction that direct interaction emphasizes the informative aspect rather than the emotional entertainment aspect for respondents. Overall, this series of findings supports the Stimulus-Organism-Response (S-O-R) theory model, in which digital marketing stimuli influence consumers' internal conditions, which then generate specific behavioral responses. Despite variations in the role of emotions as mediators, the TikTok Shop platform has proven successful in integrating lifestyle, promotion, and interaction to create a highly dynamic and impulsive shopping ecosystem. Understanding this process is crucial for businesses to design strategies that are not only informative but also capable of appealing to consumers' emotional side.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study concludes that shopping behavior on TikTok Shop has transformed into a part of identity and lifestyle that provides emotional satisfaction for consumers. Data analysis shows that Shopping Lifestyle and Flash Sale have a significant influence in evoking Positive Emotions and encouraging Impulse Buying. Flash sale programs have proven to be an effective psychological tool for cutting through consumers' rational considerations through the urgency effect. On the other hand, although Live Streaming is not strong enough to drastically change consumers' moods (Positive Emotions), this feature still has the power to turn viewing intentions into spontaneous purchasing actions through two-way communication that provides instant confidence.

Furthermore, Positive Emotions were found to play a significant mediating role in the influence of Shopping Lifestyle and Flash Sale on Impulse Buying. This indicates that consumers' enthusiasm for trends and price offers must first go through a stage of arousing feelings of joy and excitement before finally breaking down self-control and triggering spontaneous transactions. However, positive emotions were not found to mediate the relationship between Live Streaming and impulsive buying. Spontaneous purchases during live streaming sessions are more driven by informative factors such as the clarity of product demonstrations and the credibility of the host, rather than changes in the audience's mood. As a recommendation, the TikTok Shop platform and business actors are advised to revitalize their live streaming strategies by packaging content in a more creative entertainment format (shoppertainment) to evoke the emotional side of viewers. Sellers also need to integrate limited offers with current trends that are popular through more personalized algorithms to maximize emotional impact. For future researchers, it is recommended to expand the SOR theory model by integrating other variables relevant to the digital economy, such as Fear of Missing Out (FOMO), User Generated Content (UGC), and the role of influencers.

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